

SOME ASPECTS OF HOUSING IN UZBEKISTAN IN 1991-2021

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Abstract: Since gaining its independence, Uzbekistan has implemented a number of housing reforms. The basis of these reforms is the provision of quality and affordable housing. As a result, a number of measures have been taken to provide housing for the population between 1991 and 2021. During the Soviet era, housing construction was carried out in four ways - at the expense of the local budget, enterprises and organizations, at the expense of housing cooperatives, or by allocating land for the construction of buildings for the population and government assistance.

Key words: Independence, housing policy, “Tashkentuyjoyjamgarmabanki”, Uzagrokurilish, Uzbektransqurilish Association, Uzsuvqurilish Concern.

Since the early days of independence, a new approach has been taken to providing housing for the population. It is expedient to consider this in the case of Tashkent. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a decree on January 31, 1996 "On strengthening state support for housing construction in Tashkent." Residents of Tashkent had the right to buy houses on these bank bonds. 50 percent of the value of housing purchased by the population on bonds is covered from the state budget. In the first year of the establishment of “Tashkentoyjoyjamgarmabanki”, 2198 individuals opened their bank accounts. 1561 of them paid the first installment for the apartment they were going to buy and were able to get a loan from the bank. The bank loan was issued for a period of 10 years and was repaid at a rate not exceeding 20% [1].

The newspaper "O'zbekiston ovozi" talks about the measures taken in the mid-1990s to provide housing for the population and lists the advantages of buying a house through "Tashkentuyjoyjamg'armabank". In particular, the newspaper writes:

“So, what were these benefits for housing? First and foremost, 50 percent of the cost of housing construction is covered by the budget the state. Second, it is enough for future homeowners to buy a package of housing bonds equal to 20% of the total value of the house to buy it, and the remaining amount is long-term, provided that the debt is repaid within 10 years, taking into account the budget. gets a concessional loan. Another important point is that the income used by citizens to buy housing bonds and repay bank loans is not taxed [2].

In 1996, the Tashkent city administration allocated land in the city center for the construction of 1,000 apartments. The design institutes prepared the necessary documents within a month. Tashkentoyjoyjamgarmabanki Corporation was the general contractor for the construction of the bonds. Republican organizations such as Uzpromstroy Corporation, Uzagrokurilish, Uzbektransqurilish Association and Uzsubqurilish Concern are also involved in this work. The progress of construction is under the constant control of city and district administrations. In 1996, when housing construction began in a new order, 15 buildings with 216 apartments were commissioned under the bonds. Construction of another 636 apartments was nearing completion. Concessional loans worth 491 million soums were allocated for the construction of housing on the bonds. The engineering facilities of these settlements - drinking and sewage, gas, electricity, telephones - were brought to the first well at the expense of the budget [3].

Since the 2000s, Uzbekistan has taken drastic measures to provide housing for certain categories of the population. Particular attention is paid to the provision of housing for teachers, military personnel and young families. In this process, the requirements of the population groups working or serving in which area were taken into account. In other words, if there is a need for housing in any area, it is necessary to build housing for the population of that area.

In particular, in 2005 a new school No. 31 was built in Malikabad village of Kyzyltepa district of Navoi region. Later, young people who had graduated from the

university entered the school. In order to provide housing for these young teachers, houses for teachers will be built in 2012 in this village. These houses were given to teachers on the basis of long-term loans. Ochilova Oyubbi, a correspondent for the Ma'rifat newspaper, will talk to Rano Aslanova, the director of the letter, about the houses. In particular, the director expresses his opinion about the houses: "We also live in one of such houses. I live side by side with my colleagues Nilufarhon Hamroeva, Feruza Yarashova, Nozima Jalalova. Of course, the factors that underpin the effectiveness of teachers are, first of all, the requirements of the agenda, the healthy, creative dominance of the school, and secondly, the creation of opportunities in their homes that do not lag behind the city and the development of rural infrastructure [4].

After 2010, the construction of houses for young people and young families began in several regions of Uzbekistan. These houses were known among the population mainly as "Kamolot" houses. Couples who have achieved high results in science, art, literature, sports and other areas, and who were not older than thirty at the time of application, had the right to purchase Kamolot houses on the basis of a mortgage loan. Relevant documents for this purpose were submitted to the regional councils of the youth social movement "Kamolot" and through them submitted to the central council of the movement [5].

In 2014, houses for activists of the social movement "Kamolot" were built in several cities of Uzbekistan, and these houses were called "Kamolot". In particular, this year Kamolat houses for young people have been built in Andijan city of Andijan region and in Asaka and Balikchi districts. The 48-apartment high-rise buildings in Andijan were built by And-Konstrakshn LLC.

The available sources also allow us to consider this issue in the case of Tashkent region. In connection with the Year of the Healthy Child in 2014, it is planned to build 1,050 houses for young families in Tashkent region on the basis of standard projects. In addition, this year 192 young families received soft loans for

housing. In some cases, attempts have been made to achieve this by reconstructing dwellings that are no longer in use or in disrepair. In particular, in 2014, 65-apartment multi-storey houses were reconstructed in Angren, and these apartments were given to young families. These apartments consisted of 1, 2, and 3 bedroom houses. These apartments were provided to young employees of the Angren city administration and JSC "Angren Coal" and 65 young families, including activists of the youth social movement "Kamolot" on a soft loan [6].

In recent years, the construction of "Kamolot" houses has continued. In particular, in 2015, it is planned to build more than 50 "Kamolot" houses in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent, consisting of 64 multi-storey apartments. In particular, in 2015, two Kamolot houses were commissioned in Shukur Burhanov mahalla in Sergeli district of Tashkent. The construction of these houses was financed by the Sergeli branch of the National Bank for Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Chilanar branch of Uzpromstroybank, each of which consisted of 32 apartments [7].

In 2017-2021, a number of measures have been taken to provide state support to children deprived of parental care. One of them was the issue of providing housing for these children. In particular, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 9, 2021 "On measures to introduce a new system of state support for orphans and children deprived of parental care" the privilege is additionally exempted from property tax, provided that they are valid until the age of 23 for housing provided by the state [8].

In particular, on December 9, 2021, a meeting of the Senate Committee on Youth, Culture and Sports was held in Tashkent city administration. According to the meeting, a total of 173 houses for orphans and children deprived of parental care will be purchased in Tashkent in 2021. A total of 29.583 million soums has been allocated for this work. Of this, 14.792 million were allocated from the national

budget and 14.792 million from local budgets. According to the Tashkent city administration, 149 Chinese orphans were provided with housing in 2019-2021[9].

In conclusion, the provision of housing for the population in 1991-2021 was considered as one of the priorities of state policy. While before 2000 the work was carried out mainly to provide the population with housing through a certain economic support, since 2010 the tendency to build houses for the population has increased in the provision of housing.

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